

Behind The Screen: A Phenomenological Study on the Well-Being of Content Moderators in Davao City

Kenneth R. Alquino, Rpm

Master's Degree Student, School of Counseling and Psychology, San Pedro College, Philippines

Mary Ann Rose C. Bartolo, PhD, LPT, RGC

VP Admin/Director, HRDO, San Pedro College, Philippines

Abstract

Content moderators evaluate online content, including graphic or disturbing material, yet their crucial role remains undervalued, with limited research on their well-being, especially in Davao City. This study addresses that gap by exploring their lived experiences, focusing on job characteristics, perceived advantages, challenges, coping strategies, and gained insights. Through a descriptive phenomenological method, the study involved ten purposively selected content moderators with at least one year of exposure to graphic content, who were interviewed in a psychologist-supervised counseling room using a semi-structured guide. Colaizzi's thematic method guided the analysis, and five additional individuals were chosen for data triangulation to enhance credibility. Findings revealed that content moderators were motivated by recognition, career growth, and a sense of purpose. However, despite these advantages, they faced high demands, limited autonomy, and intense cognitive, emotional, and physical stress, leading to altered perceptions, emotional exhaustion, physical discomfort, and feelings of isolation due to workplace secrecy. Moderators were also expected to maintain precision in their work, even amidst procedural inconsistencies and evasion tactics. With these challenges, moderators relied on peer and organizational support and used strategies such as cognitive restructuring, diversionary activities, and establishing emotional boundaries. Through their experiences, they gained insights into responsible social media engagement, the role of human involvement, and the importance of mental well-being and work-life balance. The study highlights the need for responsible social media usage and stronger support systems. It calls for greater involvement from families, mental health professionals, and organizations to assist moderators in sustaining their well-being.

Keywords: *Content Moderators, Content Moderation, Social Media, Graphic Content, Well-Being.*

Suggested citation: Alquino, K.R., & Bartolo, M.A.R.C. (2025). Behind The Screen: A Phenomenological Study on the Well-Being of Content Moderators in Davao City. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(4), 241-255. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(4).16

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

Content moderators are essential in ensuring that online content adheres to regulations and is suitable for users. They constantly evaluate content to maintain the usefulness and profitability of online platforms (Gerrard, 2022; Drootin, 2021). Their work typically involves moderating content related to themes of violence, harassment, child pornography, drugs, murder, and self-harm. Despite their contributions, they encounter significant psychological challenges due to graphic content exposure, raising a critical concern, particularly in Davao City, where there is a notable lack of information on how they manage the demands of their profession.

Content moderators are vulnerable to psychological harm due to repeated exposure to graphic content, which can lead to aggression, reduced empathy, depression, burnout, and PTSD (Anderson et al., 2017; University of Southern California, 2019). Research shows that they often develop emotional detachment, experience changes in intimacy and sexuality, and suffer from intrusive thoughts and exhaustion (Dosoño & Semaan, 2019; Riedl et al., 2020; Spence et al., 2023). Despite their critical role, moderators receive limited recognition or support, prompting Steiger et al. (2021) to call for further research. In the Philippines, a study by Bharucha et al. (2023) on Filipino moderators revealed common emotional and physical reactions to graphic content, including fear, disgust, increased heart rate, and headaches.

Emerging global and local studies recognize the vital role of content moderators but also highlight the challenges they face. Despite growing interest, research on Filipino moderators remains limited, particularly in Davao City. Steiger et al. (2021) and Bharucha et al. (2023) called for further research to address existing gaps, primarily through lived interviews. Responding to this need, the present study uses a descriptive phenomenological design to explore the experiences of Davao-based content moderators, focusing on job characteristics, perceived benefits, challenges, coping strategies, and insights influenced by personal and environmental factors. It also examines emotional and organizational stressors, the role of peer and institutional support, and the relevance of tailored wellness programs. Findings aim to inform moderators and their families, mental health professionals, and future researchers, promoting a deeper understanding of this high-stress occupation.

Materials and Methods

The study used a descriptive phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of content moderators in Davao City. The interviews were conducted in a private counseling room within a local institution, supervised by a registered psychologist.

The study involved ten purposively selected content moderators from Davao, meeting Hennink and Kaiser's (2022) data saturation criteria. Moderators had at least one year of experience moderating graphic content in various formats. The group included five males and five females, aged 24 to 29, with no diagnosed trauma- or stress-related disorders. All provided informed consent. To strengthen trustworthiness, the study included five additional participants for data triangulation.

In-depth interviews were conducted with content moderators using a flexible, open-ended protocol to gather rich data and identify emerging themes (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Data from ten moderators and five triangulation participants were manually transcribed and analyzed using Colaizzi's method under the JDCS model (Karasek &

Theorell, 1990) and the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) lenses. The researcher employed strategies such as member checking, thematic saturation, thick descriptions, persistent observations, methodological notes, and an audit trail to ensure trustworthiness. Information was securely stored and will be retained for five years per APA Ethical Standard 6.01 (Berenson, 2018).

Results and Discussion

Content Moderators' Experiences Regarding the Job Characteristics of Screening Graphic Content

Theme 1: The Complex and Demanding Nature of Content Moderation

Moderators in this study identified accuracy as a central job demand. Content often falls into grey areas, appearing inappropriate initially but not necessarily violating platform policies. As a result, they must carefully interpret content about multiple guidelines to determine whether it can be posted. This supports existing findings highlighting the stress of maintaining over 95% accuracy and adhering to performance metrics (Dwoskin et al., 2019).

Moderators also revealed that violations can be subtle or hidden, requiring them to review across different formats. Some reported following up to 68 separate guidelines, which are frequently updated, echoing Gillespie's (2018) observation that platform growth, legal shifts, and public pressure influenced ongoing changes in policies. In this study, moderators expressed that these constant changes demand ongoing learning and adaptation, often leading to frustration.

Moreover, moderators described the sheer volume of content as a demand, as they reviewed content between 100 and 3,000 items daily. This demand is also reflected in prior research (Gillespie, 2018; Spence et al., 2023), intensifying emotional labor, especially when handling graphic material.

Furthermore, moderators reported time pressure as an additional demand, with content often reviewed in 20–30 seconds (Mukhopadhyay, 2020), contributing to stress and reduced emotional well-being (Baethge et al., 2018). Existing literature supports this study's findings, emphasizing the psychological and emotional toll of content moderation demands.

Theme 2: Control and Autonomy in Content Moderation

Sense of control plays a vital role in helping content moderators manage stress in a high-demand environment. Moderators reported having some control, such as voicing opinions and suggesting guideline changes. However, management often makes final decisions, making some feel like "just employees" with reactive roles. Others expressed frustration over the strict adherence required to company policies, which limited their autonomy. Gillespie (2018) explains that platform policies limit moderators' autonomy and may stem from strict precision demands and frequent quality audits (Dwoskin et al., 2019).

Despite these constraints, moderators acknowledged the importance of guidelines in maintaining a structured process. Moreover, minimal control exists in areas like work scheduling, with organizations accommodating requests for adjustments, particularly for mental health reasons. Existing research has shown that job control influences employee well-being, where greater autonomy boosts motivation and satisfaction while reducing burnout and stress (Putri & Radikun, 2023).

Overall, moderators balance limited autonomy in decision-making and the ability to influence specific aspects of their work environment, highlighting the dual nature of their control within the role.

Theme 3: Comprehensive Organizational and Peer Support in Content Moderation

With these demands and a mixed sense of control, organizational support remains evident in significantly influencing their experiences by addressing their well-being and job demands, as prior studies presented how the lack of support in content moderation could negatively affect mental health (Newton, 2019, 2020; Dosono & Semaan, 2019). Moderators reported experiencing various interventions that built their resilience and managed the psychological impact of graphic content exposure (Steiger et al., 2021; Compton & Shim, 2020).

Moderators reported benefiting from various workplace resources, including wellness activities, operational support like training and guidelines updates, and logistical assistance such as shuttle services and free meals. Existing research proposed these job characteristics as essential for mitigating stress and exhaustion and improving job commitment (Sazkaya & Görmezoğlu, 2021).

Apart from organizational support, moderators found comfort and validation through peer camaraderie, reinforcing a supportive work dynamic. This aligns with studies showing that peer support enhances resilience and coping while reducing distress (Agarwal et al., 2020). In this study, moderators acknowledged the comfort derived from their shared experiences and mutual understanding, aligning with previous research on how volunteer moderators felt appreciated and supported when they connected with others who shared similar experiences (Dosono & Semaan, 2019).

Advantages That Motivate Content Moderators to Fulfil Their Roles

Theme 1: Recognition and Validation as Motivational Drivers

Moderators acknowledged efforts as fulfilling, highlighting that feeling recognized by others for the value of their work contributes to lightening the mood and a sense of fulfillment. They also noted the satisfaction of knowing their work is meaningful, even if not fully understood by the public. Moderators echoed this sentiment, emphasizing that fulfillment is derived from the nature of the job itself. Moderators described themselves as "hidden heroes" who positively influence society. This aligns with research showing the relationship between recognition, motivation, job satisfaction, and performance (Waghe et al., 2023; Spence et al., 2023). The findings also suggest that recognition validates efforts and assists moderators in reframing stressful experiences as meaningful, consistent with the transactional model of stress and coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

Theme 2: Workplace Motivators and Opportunities for Personal and Professional Growth

Moderators' responses reveal a range of motivations that sustain their roles and support career and personal growth. Job characteristics and financial incentives were key drivers, with many drawn to the non-voice, remote, and flexible nature of content moderation, which is less taxing than voice-based work (Dwoskin et al., 2019; Nicholson, 2018). Moderators disclosed that flexibility helped them manage psychological strain despite strict guidelines and accuracy demands. Although often overlooked in moderation research, studies on similar roles highlight how flexible

scheduling improves well-being, work-life balance, and job satisfaction (Elnanto & Suharti, 2021; Ray & Pana-Cryan, 2021).

This study also reveals a previously underexplored motivator in content moderation: workplace rewards and benefits. Moderators cited salary adjustments, bonuses, and other incentives as key to sustaining their commitment, findings that align with research in other fields (Nur'aeni et al., 2022). Moderators also viewed employment at a well-known platform and access to restricted content as privileges, contributing to a sense of pride and identity. This supports existing research on brand reputation as a motivational factor (Kumar & Sathish, 2021; Sharma, 2019), though its specific role in content moderation remains underexamined.

Additionally, moderators noted that the role builds transferable skills, boosts career prospects, and fosters resilience, discipline, and mental readiness, deepening job commitment. Although not widely studied in content moderation, research shows that ongoing training and skill development enhance performance and motivation (Macur, 2024).

Theme 3: Sense of Purpose and Responsibility in Protecting Online Spaces

A sense of purpose emerged as a new theme in this study, one not widely explored in prior content moderation literature. Moderators see themselves as protectors or heroes, working behind the scenes to protect vulnerable groups from distressing content.

Though often unrecognized, they exhibit courage, self-sacrifice, and a strong drive to protect others, traits aligned with Kinsella et al.'s (2015) concept of workplace heroes. Moderators' sense of meaningful work aligns with Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) model, where challenging roles are appraised as valuable. Van Wingerden and Van der Stoep's (2018) findings show that perceived meaning enhances engagement. Similarly, Kinsella et al. (2019) found that heroic behavior fosters purpose, supporting sustained commitment.

Moderators' heroic actions could also be traced to their cultural values. Their desire to protect others reflects "*kapwa*" (shared identity) and "*Bayanihan*" (communal unity), where personal responsibility is tied to collective well-being (Enriquez, 1978; Bersamira & Macaraeg, 2022). Overall, the findings proposed that moderators appraised their roles as a technical and moral duty rooted in cultural and social identity.

Challenges Content Moderators Encounter in Moderating Graphic Content

Theme 1: Systemic and Personal Barriers to Effective Moderation

Precision remains a demanding aspect of the content moderation role, considering how inaccurate ratings can lead to various complications. Based on moderators' responses, individual differences in understanding guidelines, influenced by cultural background and biases, lead to inconsistencies in content evaluation and decision-making. Research highlights the role's demand for precision amid shifting guidelines (Gillespie, 2018; Dwoskin et al., 2019), with varied interpretations complicating moderation (Suzor et al., 2019). While regular evaluations aim to reduce bias (Southern, 2023), they may also heighten job strain.

Moderators reported that users and content creators often find ways to bypass community guidelines, making moderation more difficult. As platforms refine their policies to catch violations (Gerrard, 2018), users also improve their evasion tactics, allowing harmful content to spread (Huertas-García et al., 2022). Moderators found

this cycle overwhelming, as they must constantly adapt to changing guidelines while maintaining accuracy.

Moreover, moderators felt frustrated, guilty, and helpless as they were limited to tagging or deleting content and unable to act beyond moderation policies despite the harm of repeated exposure to graphic content. These feelings are further exacerbated by the inefficiencies in the moderating systems, such as inadequate oversight from other companies and moderators, highlighting concerns about harmful content reaching vulnerable groups. This aligns with existing research, as limited decision-making power contributes to cognitive stress (Putri & Radikun, 2023; Taouk et al., 2024).

Non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) contribute to emotional isolation and a lack of public understanding among moderators; a concern reflected in the present study. Roberts (2019) noted that NDAs prevent moderators from discussing their work, fostering isolation, while Spence et al. (2023) emphasized that they create a culture of silence, deterring disclosure even when moderators are distressed or harmed.

Theme 2: Negative Cognitive Shifts through Content Moderation

Negative cognitive shifts were evident based on the moderators' responses. Many reported altered worldviews, erosion of trust, and cognitive dissonance, with some developing fear, anxiety, and hypervigilance, even in otherwise safe environments, echoing findings from prior studies (Spence et al., 2023; Steiger et al., 2021). Moreover, a notable finding was the development of mistrust among female moderators who reported difficulty trusting men, which Hatamleh et al. (2023) emphasized as a critical factor in shaping social relationships in virtual environments.

Theme 3: Psychological and Emotional Toll from Graphic Exposure

Content moderators, due to constant exposure to distressing material, often experience emotional desensitization, boundary struggles, intrusive thoughts, and symptoms associated with PTSD, including flashbacks, sleep disturbances, and persistent distress (Spence et al., 2024; Benjelloun & Otherman, 2020). This study's findings align with prior research showing heightened emotional and physiological reactions, such as startle responses, increased heart rate, and sweating when viewing graphic content (Hartman et al., 2021; Bharucha et al., 2023). These outcomes reinforce the connection between content moderation and PTSD-related symptoms.

Content involving children and animal cruelty intensified emotional distress. Spence et al. (2023) noted that moderators often avoid child-related content due to its disturbing nature and protective emotional responses. Given the demands of constant exposure to graphic content, moderators are prone to exhaustion and emotional exhaustion, which aligns with several studies highlighting burnout (Spence et al., 2023; Brady, 2017). This burnout often leads to behavioral changes, which moderators in this study reported, such as avoiding certain activities and disruptions to work-life balance.

Theme 4: Physical Health and Behavioral Impacts of Stress

Moderators reported physical and behavioral effects of stress, including appetite loss and nausea, especially after viewing graphic content involving bodily fluids. While past studies link social media exposure to food and body image issues (Blanchard et al., 2023; Filippone et al., 2022), this study highlights similar effects within the professional context of content moderation. The findings revealed that frequent exposure to pornographic content affected some moderators' sexual responses, with a few

reporting increased arousal, aligning with related studies establishing their connection (Charmley, 2022).

Content Moderators' Coping Strategies in Response to the Challenges They Experience

Theme 1: Utilizing Workplace Support Systems for Stress Relief

Moderators' responses highlight a shared experience among them, emphasizing emotional support and shared understanding as crucial coping mechanisms. Moderators relied on workplace support systems to cope with the demands of their role, drawing strength from colleagues and wellness programs. Guided by Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) transactional model and the JDCS model (Karasek & Theorell, 1990), they assessed resources and emphasized the value of strong workplace relationships. The study found that organizational support, mental health resources, and peer venting fostered emotional relief, security, and belonging. This aligns with Compton and Shim (2020), who emphasized therapy and support in sustaining employee well-being.

Existing studies presented peer support as vital in promoting resilience and mental health by fostering connection, self-esteem, and coping while reducing loneliness and distress (Agarwal, Brooks, & Greenberg, 2020; Dosono & Semaan, 2019). However, NDAs often prevent moderators from seeking external support (Roberts, 2018). In this study, moderators confided in their colleagues instead, as they could better understand their challenges, echoing Spence et al. (2024). However, while peer support offers emotional relief, the researcher in this study also notes its potential downside, as a reciprocal emotional burden and burnout may manifest.

Theme 2: Reconstructing and Adjusting Cognitively and Emotionally to Challenges

Cognitive restructuring was evident as moderators reframed challenges as part of the job, focusing on solutions rather than problems. These findings align with the statements from participants in data triangulation, who described how moderators often feel they have no choice but to engage with the content they moderate, as it is an inherent part of their job. Moderators focused on solutions and maintained a professional mindset, aligning with Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) view that reinterpretation reduces distress and Riepenhausen et al.'s (2022) meta-analysis, which identifies positive cognitive reappraisal as a key resilience factor. Moreover, moderators in this study reported becoming desensitized over time, reducing their emotional reactions (Bharucha et al., 2023). While desensitization can offer short-term relief, it does not apply to all content and may mask underlying emotional fatigue, potentially delaying burnout (Spence et al., 2023).

Theme 3: Managing Stress through Diversionary Activities and Emotional Expression

Moderators used emotion-focused strategies like diversionary activities (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Leisure activities such as hiking, exercise, and gaming were typical and helped reduce stress, aligning with studies linking these activities to improved mental health (Takiguchi et al., 2022). Spence et al. (2023) and Bharucha et al. (2023) found similar patterns, highlighting these activities as grounding and therapeutic.

While this study highlighted positive coping strategies, some moderators reported using social drinking for stress relief. This reflects findings from Almroth et al. (2022), who linked high-strain jobs to increased alcohol use, especially among men. Roberts

(2019) similarly found that content moderators often turn to alcohol to manage stress. Moderators in this study also noted that social drinking is common across the BPO industry, echoing Bulaon-Ducusin (2017) and Camello (2020), who observed similar coping patterns among call center agents. A key finding of this study is the use of humor and emotional expression, such as crying, as coping strategies among content moderators, contrary to most existing literature on content moderation. While humor and crying have been widely recognized in this field, studies in other areas suggest they boost well-being and reduce negative emotions (Schneider et al., 2018; Sharman et al., 2020). The use of humor aligns with Filipino cultural traits of finding laughter in adversity (Litam & Chan, 2022).

Theme 4: Managing Well-being through Emotional and Behavioral Boundaries.

Moderators adopted strategies to establish emotional and behavioral boundaries between their professional responsibilities and personal well-being. They reported setting clear limits between work and personal life through emotional disengagement. These strategies included adaptive and maladaptive forms of disengagement, such as emotional detachment and intentional rest, to manage stress (Waugh, Shing, & Furr, 2020). While these approaches offered temporary relief, high levels of avoidance coping have been linked to poorer well-being (Allen, 2021). Moderators also balanced empathy with emotional distancing to maintain professionalism, a coping mechanism noted in previous studies (Dosono & Semaan, 2019; Spence et al., 2023). This emotional separation served as a form of self-protection rather than a lack of empathy, highlighting a key area for further research.

Insights Content Moderators Gained from Their Experiences Moderating Graphic Content

Theme 1: The Intersection of Social Media, Human Behavior, and Responsible Engagement

Content moderators recognized the influence of social media on users. Previous studies link social media to negative outcomes like smartphone addiction (Ali et al., 2023), cyberbullying (Cook, 2024), and harmful content sharing (Soron & Islam, 2020; Cero & Witte, 2020). Content moderators, shaped by repeated exposure to graphic material, advocated for safer online spaces, especially for minors, viewing social media primarily through its risks. Gerbner's Cultivation Theory (1969) helps explain how constant exposure to graphic content shapes moderators' perceptions, often reinforcing a negative view of social media. This aligns with Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) transactional model, where moderators appraise social media as a threat based on perceived risks. Spence et al. (2023) similarly found that prolonged exposure may alter moderators' psychological outlook. These insights suggest that extended contact with disturbing content significantly shapes moderators' perceptions of the digital world.

Theme 2: The Critical Role of Human Moderators in Effective Content Moderation

Moderators shared insights emphasizing their crucial roles in filtering inappropriate or harmful content, believing that without them, social media would become chaotic and unsafe, especially for vulnerable groups. To manage the high content volume, organizations rely on artificial intelligence (AI) to assist in moderation (Caplan, 2018; Walker, 2023). However, moderators highlighted AI's limitations in making complex judgment calls and emphasized the irreplaceable value of human involvement. While

AI proves effective in flagging certain violations (Canales, 2021), its limitations persist, as it can mislabel content due to a lack of context and miss subtle, culturally specific issues (Gillespie, 2018). Moderators in this study echoed the view that human judgment remains critical (Gillespie, 2020). Through their narratives, the researcher in this study observed how they understood their responsibilities, acknowledged the limitations of AI, and emphasized the need for human involvement in content filtering.

Theme 3: Growth Through the Realities and Challenges of Content Moderation Work

Another theme that emerged from moderators' responses and insights focused on the growth and transformation they experience through the challenges and realities of content moderation. Moderators emphasized the gap between the common misconceptions and the real challenges of content moderation. For instance, while outsiders often perceive the job as straightforward, moderators described it as far more complex, requiring technical skills and emotional resilience. Many moderators disclosed underestimating the job's demands, assuming it would be routine; however, they quickly learned the emotionally challenging aspect of the role. This change reflects the JDACS model (Karasek & Theorell, 1990), Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) appraisal process, and Gerbner's (1969) Cultivation Theory, which explains how prolonged exposure shapes one's perspective. Moreover, moderators reported personal growth, gaining critical thinking, cultural awareness, and emotional resilience. Despite challenges, organizational support, through training and peer connections, helped buffer stress, consistent with studies showing that adequate support improves well-being and performance (Shiri et al., 2023; Macur, 2024).

Theme 4: Prioritizing Well-Being and Work-Life Balance for Mental Health

Moderators emphasized the importance of prioritizing mental health, considering the emotional demands of their work. They shared that seeking support from peers, family, and professionals helps them manage psychological challenges and stressed the need to normalize vulnerability. Additionally, they underscored the value of setting firm boundaries between professional responsibilities and personal life. While committed to promoting online safety, moderators believed preventing work from encroaching on their personal spaces was essential. These insights align with the Job Demand-Control-Support (JDACS) model (Karasek & Theorell, 1990), which identifies support as a critical buffer against stress, and the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), which explains how individuals appraise and respond to job-related stressors. Their experiences highlight the significance of wellness programs and boundary-setting as protective strategies. These findings are consistent with existing research showing that organizational and peer support can reduce mental health risks (Compton & Shim, 2020; Dosono & Semaan, 2019) and that intentional rest fosters psychological recovery (Spence et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Theoretically, this study extends the JDACS model by suggesting that content moderation involves high demands, low control, and significant emotional labor, an area the model overlooks. Incorporating the transactional model fills this gap, highlighting moderators' emotional appraisals and coping strategies and how these shape their experiences. Findings suggest that content moderation is defined not only by organizational-specific demands but also by complex emotional processes

reinforced by the need for diverse, integrated theoretical frameworks. Future research may explore how partial autonomy and differentiated types of support influence well-being and job satisfaction.

Practically, the study highlights the need for tailored organizational interventions. While support systems exist, their effectiveness varies, highlighting the importance of refining wellness programs to align with moderators' needs. Although organizations have integrated artificial intelligence into the profession, human judgment remains indispensable in assessing complex violations. This suggests further refining AI-assisted tools to handle preliminary filtering while reducing moderators' exposure to extreme content.

Building on these practical implications, the study highlights the critical role of mental health practitioners in evaluating and enhancing support programs that are culturally and individually responsive. For moderators, the findings imply that recognition, positive coping strategies, and autonomy are vital in maintaining commitment and well-being. At the same time, families may serve as crucial sources of emotional support, helping mitigate the psychological burdens moderators face despite disclosure limitations. Ultimately, the study's findings challenged negative perceptions of content moderation, highlighting it as a meaningful career with various advantages. It also calls on social media users to act responsibly and report violations, recognizing that moderation is a shared responsibility that impacts broader digital well-being.

References

- Agarwal, B., Brooks, S. K., & Greenberg, N. (2020). The role of peer support in managing occupational stress: A qualitative study of the sustaining resilience at work intervention. *Workplace Health & Safety*, 68(2), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2165079919873934>
- Ali, A. A., Babiker, A., Erbad, A., & Ali, R. (2023). Intentions matter: The role of purpose in excessive social media usage and smartphone addiction. In *2023 10th International Conference on Behavioural and Social Computing (BESC)* (pp. 1–7). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BESC59560.2023.10386530>
- Allen, M. T. (2021). Explorations of avoidance and approach coping and perceived stress with a computer-based avatar task: Detrimental effects of resignation and withdrawal. *PeerJ*, 9, e11265. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.11265>
- Anderson, C. A., Bushman, B. J., Bartholow, B. D., Cantor, J., Christakis, D., Coyne, S. M., Donnerstein, E., Brockmyer, J. F., Gentile, D. A., Green, C. S., Huesmann, R., Hummer, T., Krahé, B., Strasburger, V. C., Warburton, W., Wilson, B. J., & Ybarra, M. (2017). Screen violence and youth behavior. *Pediatrics*, 140(Suppl 2), S142–S147. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1758T>
- Baethge, A., Vahle-Hinz, T., Schulte-Braucks, J., & van Dick, R. (2018). A matter of time? Challenging and hindering effects of time pressure on work engagement. *Work & Stress*, 32(3), 228–247. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678373.2017.1415998>
- Benjelloun, R., & Otheman, Y. (2020). Psychological distress in a social media content moderator: A case report. *Archives of Psychiatry and Mental Health*, 4, 73–75.
- Berenson, K. R. (2018). *Managing your research data and documentation*. American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0000068-000>

- Bharucha, T., Steiger, M. E., Manchanda, P., Mere, R., & Huang, X. (2024). Content moderator startle response: A qualitative study. In X. S. Yang, R. S. Sherratt, N. Dey, & A. Joshi (Eds.), *Proceedings of Eighth International Congress on Information and Communication Technology. ICICT 2023* (Vol. 695, pp. 695). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-3043-2_184
- Blanchard, L., Conway-Moore, K., Aguiar, A., Önal, F., Rutter, H., Helleve, A., Nwosu, E., Falcone, J., Savona, N., Boyland, E., & Knai, C. (2023). Associations between social media, adolescent mental health, and diet: A systematic review. *Obesity Reviews: An Official Journal of the International Association for the Study of Obesity*, 24(Suppl 2), e13631. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13631>
- Brady, P. Q. (2017). Crimes against caring: Exploring the risk of secondary traumatic stress, burnout, and compassion satisfaction among child exploitation investigators. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 32(4), 305–318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11896-016-9223-8>
- Bulaon-Ducusin, G. (2017, October 6). Call center agents prone to obesity, study says. *Se&T Media Service*. <https://www.dost.gov.ph/knowledge-resources/news/48-2017-news/1298-call-center-agents-prone-to-obesity-study-says.html>
- Camello, K. J. C. (2020). Lifestyle practices, dietary pattern, and nutritional status of call center agents. *Asian Journal of Health (Liceo de Cagayan University)*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.7828/ajoh.v9i1.1305>
- Canales, K. (2021, March 26). Mark Zuckerberg said content moderation requires “nuances” that consider the intent behind a post, but also highlighted Facebook’s reliance on AI to do that job. *Business Insider*. <https://www.businessinsider.com/zuckerberg-nuances-content-moderation-ai-misinformation-hearing-2021-3>
- Caplan, R. (2018, November 14). Content or context moderation? *Data & Society*. <https://datasociety.net/library/content-or-context-moderation/>
- Cero, I., & Witte, T. K. (2020). Assortativity of suicide-related posting on social media. *American Psychologist*, 75(3), 365–379. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000477>
- Charmley, S. (2022, June 9). Sexual response cycle: Overview, phases, and more. *Medical News Today*. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/sexual-response-cycle>
- Creswell, J., & Poth, C. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Compton, M. T., & Shim, R. S. (2020, September 1). Mental illness prevention and mental health promotion: When, who, and how. *Psychiatric Services (Washington, D.C.)*, 71(9), 981–983. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ps.201900374>
- Cook, S. (2024, January 10). *Cyberbullying statistics and facts for 2024*. Comparitech. <https://www.comparitech.com/internet-providers/cyberbullying-statistics/>
- Dosono, B., & Semaan, B. (2019). Moderation practices as emotional labor in sustaining online communities: The case of AAPI identity work on Reddit. In *CHI '19: Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–13). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300372>

- Drootin, A. (2021). “Community guidelines”: The legal implications of workplace conditions for internet content moderators. *Fordham Law Review*, 90(3), 1197–1244. <https://ir.lawnet.fordham.edu/flr/vol90/iss3/4/>
- Dwoskin, E., Whalen, J., & Cabato, R. (2019, July 25). Content moderators at YouTube, Facebook and Twitter see the worst. *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2019/07/25/social-media-companies-are-outsourcing-their-dirty-work-philippines-generation-workers-is-paying-price/>
- Elnanto, J. G., & Suharti, L. (2021). The impact of work from home on work-life balance and its implication for employee happiness. *International Journal of Social Science and Business*, 5(3), 311–318. <https://doi.org/10.23887/ijssb.v5i3.35325>
- Enriquez, V. G. (1978). Kapwa: A core concept in Filipino social psychology. *Philippine Social Sciences and Humanities Review*, 42, 100–108.
- Filippone, L., Shankland, R., & Hallez, Q. (2022). The relationships between social media exposure, food craving, cognitive impulsivity and cognitive restraint. *Journal of Eating Disorders*, 10(1), 184. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40337-022-00698-4>
- Gerbner, G. (1969). Toward “cultural indicators”: The analysis of mass mediated public message systems. *AV Communication Review*, 17(2), 137–148.
- Gerrard, Y. (2018). Beyond the hashtag: Circumventing content moderation on social media. *New Media & Society*, 20(12), 4492–4511. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818776611>
- Gerrard, Y. (2022). Social media moderation: The best-kept secret in tech. In D. Rosen (Ed.), *The social media debate* (pp. 77–95). Routledge.
- Gillespie, T. (2020). Content moderation, AI, and the question of scale. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720943234>
- Gillespie, T. (2018). *Custodians of the internet: Platforms, content moderation, and the hidden decisions that shape social media*. Yale University Press.
- Hartman, M. E., Ladwig, M. A., & Ekkekakis, P. (2021). Contactless differentiation of pleasant and unpleasant valence: Assessment of the acoustic startle eyeblink response with infrared reflectance oculography. *Behavior Research Methods*, 53(6), 2092–2104. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-021-01555-z>
- Hatamleh, I. H. M., Safori, A. O., Habes, M., Tahat, O., Ahmad, A. K., Abdallah, R. A.-Q., & Aissani, R. (2023, July 20). Trust in social media: Enhancing social relationships. *Social Sciences*, 12(7), 416. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci12070416>
- Hennink, M., & Kaiser, B. N. (2022). Sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research: A systematic review of empirical tests. *Social Science & Medicine*, 292, 114523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114523>
- Huertas-García, Á., Martín, A., Huertas-Tato, J., & Camacho, D. (2024). Camouflage is all you need: Evaluating and enhancing transformer models robustness against camouflage adversarial attacks. *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computational Intelligence*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tetci.2024.3440181>
- Karasek, R., & Theorell, T. (1990). *Healthy work: Stress, productivity, and the reconstruction of working life*. Basic Books.

- Kinsella, E. L., Igou, E. R., & Ritchie, T. D. (2019). Heroism and the pursuit of a meaningful life. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology, 59*(4), 474–498. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022167817701002>
- Kinsella, E. L., Ritchie, T. D., & Igou, E. R. (2015). Zeroing in on heroes: A prototype analysis of hero features. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 108*(1), 114–127. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038463>
- Kumar, N., & Sathish, A. S. (2021). Understanding the influence of brand reputation and trust on loyalty: A mediated role of relationship. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology, 17*, 8441–8457.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer.
- Litam, S. D. A., & Chan, C. D. (2022). Experiences of stress and help-seeking behaviors in Filipino Americans. *International Journal for the Advancement of Counseling, 44*(4), 586–603. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10447-022-09485-x>
- Macur, A. (2024). *Impact of training on employee motivation and performance in the sports industry* (Honors thesis No. 385). Pace University, Honors College. https://digitalcommons.pace.edu/honorscollege_theses/385
- Mukhopadhyay, B. (2020, August 26). Warning: The (open) secret lives of content moderators. *Cassandra Voices*. <https://cassandravoices.com/society/warning-the-open-secret-lives-of-content-moderators/>
- Newton, C. (2020, May 13). Facebook will pay \$52 million in settlement with moderators who developed PTSD on the job. *The Verge*. <https://www.theverge.com/2020/5/12/21255870/facebook-content-moderator-settlement-scola-ptsd-mental-health>
- Newton, C. (2019, December 16). The terror queue. *The Verge*. <https://www.theverge.com/2019/12/16/21021005/google-youtube-moderators-ptsd-accenture-violent-disturbing-content-interviews-video>
- Nicholson, A. (2018, January 24). Sundance film review: “The Cleaners.” *Variety*. <https://variety.com/2018/film/reviews/the-cleaners-review-1202673932/>
- Nur'aeni, A., Ausat, A. M. A., Purnomo, Y. J., Munir, A. R., & Suherlan. (2022). Do motivation, compensation, and work environment improve employee performance: A literature review. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research, 6*(1), 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.29099/ijair.v6i1.2.678>
- Putri, R. S., & Radikun, T. B. S. (2023). The role of job control and coping strategies as moderators in the effect of emotional demands on burnout in health workers. *GUIDENA: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Psikologi Bimbingan dan Konseling, 13*(4), 885. <https://doi.org/10.24127/gdn.v13i4.8380>
- Ray, T. K., & Pana-Cryan, R. (2021). Work flexibility and work-related well-being. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18*(6), 3254. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18063254>
- Riepenhausen, A., Wackerhagen, C., Reppmann, Z. C., Deter, H.-C., Kalisch, R., Veer, I. M., & Walter, H. (2022). Positive cognitive reappraisal in stress resilience, mental health, and well-being: A comprehensive systematic review. *Emotion Review, 14*(4), 310–331. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17540739221114642>

- Riedl, M. J., Masullo, G. M., & Whipple, K. N. (2020). The downsides of digital labor: Exploring the toll incivility takes on online comment moderators. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 107, 106262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106262>
- Roberts, S. T. (2019). *Behind the screen: Content moderation in the shadows of social media*. Yale University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvhrcz0v>
- Sazkaya, M. K., & Gormezoglu, Z. (2021). The mediating role of perceived organizational support in the effects of job stress on occupational commitment: Research on nurses working in a foundation university hospital. *Bezmialem Science*, 9(4), 465–471. <https://doi.org/10.14235/bas.galenos.2021.6475>
- Schneider, P. J., & Rizoiu, M. A. (2023). The effectiveness of moderating harmful online content. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 120(34), e2307360120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2307360120>
- Sharma, A. (2019). Meaningfulness of work and perceived organizational prestige as precursors of organizational citizenship behavior. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(1), 316–323.
- Sharman, L. S., Dingle, G. A., Vingerhoets, A. J. J. M., & Vanman, E. J. (2020). Using crying to cope: Physiological responses to stress following tears of sadness. *Emotion*, 20(7), 1279–1291. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000633>
- Shiri, R., El-Metwally, A., Sallinen, M., Pöyry, M., Härmä, M., & Toppinen-Tanner, S. (2023). The role of continuing professional training or development in maintaining current employment: A systematic review. *Healthcare*, 11(21), 2900. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11212900>
- Soron, T. R., & Islam, S. M. S. (2020). Suicide on Facebook—the tales of unnoticed departure in Bangladesh. *Cambridge Prisms: Global Mental Health*, 7, e12. <https://doi.org/10.1017/gmh.2020.5>
- Southern, M. G. (2023, April 27). *YouTube addresses bias & consistency in content moderation policies*. *Search Engine Journal*. <https://www.searchenginejournal.com/youtube-addresses-bias-consistency-in-content-moderation-policies/485643/>
- Spence, R., Bifulco, A., Bradbury, P., Martellozzo, E., & DeMarco, J. (2023). The psychological impacts of content moderation on content moderators: A qualitative study. *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 17(4), Article 8. <https://doi.org/10.5817/cp2023-4-8>
- Spence, R., Bifulco, A., Bradbury, P., Martellozzo, E., & DeMarco, J. (2024). Content moderator mental health, secondary trauma, and well-being: A cross-sectional study. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 27(2), 149–155. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2023.0298>
- Steiger, M., Bharucha, T. J., Venkatagiri, S., Riedl, M. J., & Lease, M. (2021). The psychological well-being of content moderators: The emotional labor of commercial moderation and avenues for improving support. In *CHI '21: Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–14). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445092>
- Suzor, N. P., West, S. M., Quodling, A., & York, J. (2019). What do we mean when we talk about transparency? Toward meaningful transparency in commercial content moderation. *International Journal of Communication*, 13, 1526–1543. <https://ijoc.org/index.php/ijoc/article/view/9736>

- Takiguchi, Y., Matsui, M., Kikutani, M., & Ebina, K. (2022). The relationship between leisure activities and mental health: The impact of resilience and COVID-19. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being*, 15(1), 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aphw.12394>
- Taouk, Y., Aitken, Z., LaMontagne, A. D., & King, T. (2024). Persistent low job control and subsequent major depression: A prospective cohort study of Australian working males. *Social Science & Medicine*, 359, 117283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2024.117283>
- University of California, Irvine. (2019, April 17). *Media exposure to mass violence can fuel cycle of distress, 3-year longitudinal study shows*. UC Irvine News. <https://news.uci.edu/2019/04/17/media-exposure-to-mass-violence-can-fuel-cycle-of-distress-3-year-longitudinal-study-shows/>
- Van Wingerden, J., & Van der Stoep, J. (2018). The motivational potential of meaningful work: Relationships with strengths use, work engagement, and performance. *PLOS ONE*, 13(6), e0197599. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0197599>
- Waghe, A., Mulani, S., & Dambe, P. (2023). Effect of reward and recognition on employee motivation. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368425232_Effect_of_Reward_Recognition_on_Employee_Motivation
- Walker, S. (2023, November 17). *AI for content moderation: Key benefits & challenges*. Chekkee. <https://chekkee.com/benefits-challenges-of-using-ai-for-content-moderation/>
- Waugh, C. E., Shing, E. Z., & Furr, R. M. (2020). Not all disengagement coping strategies are created equal: Positive distraction, but not avoidance, can be an adaptive coping strategy for chronic life stressors. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*, 33

